

IMPACT PROPERTIES OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES STITCHED WITH Z-FIBERS

J-H Byun, S-W Song, C-H Lee, M-K Um, and B-S Hwang

*Composite Materials Lab, Korea Institute of Machinery & Materials,
66 Sangnam-dong, Changwon, Kyungnam 641-010, South Korea*

SUMMARY: In order to characterize the outstanding performance of three-dimensional (3D) composites, the low velocity impact test has been carried out. 3D fiber structures have been achieved by using the automated tape placement (ATP) process and a stitching method. Materials for the ATP and the stitching process were carbon/epoxy prepreg tapes and Kevlar fibers, respectively. Two-dimensional (2D) composites with the same stacking sequence as 3D counterparts have also been fabricated for the comparison of damage tolerance. For the assessment of damage after the impact loading, specimens were subjected to C-scan nondestructive inspection. Compression-after-impact (CAI) tests were conducted to evaluate residual compressive strength. The damage area of 3D composites was greatly reduced (30-40%) compared with that of 2D composites. Although the CAI strength did not show drastic improvement for 3D composites, the ratio of retained strength was 5-10% higher than 2D samples. The effect of stitching on the impact performance was negligible above the energy level of 35 Joules.

KEYWORDS: impact performance, automated tape placement, stitching, damage area, compression after impact strength.

INTRODUCTION

Laminated composite materials are liable to fatal damage under impact load during the part production or in service. In this type of material, delamination is the most frequent mode of failure due to the fact that they have no reinforcement in the thickness direction. [1-3] To overcome the inherent weakness of laminate composites, three-dimensional (3D) reinforcements can be the most effective method. [4, 5] Although 3D fibrous preforms can be made by braiding or weaving, the production rate is slow due to many fiber bundles interlacing several layers. The size of 3D perform is also limited and dependent on the capacity of textile machines. The most productive and viable way of introducing through-thickness fibers is the stitching process. After carrying out the stitching on the stacked 2D fabrics, they are manufactured for composite parts by RTM (Resin Transfer Molding) or RFI (Resin Film Infusion) processes [6]. Although RTM process attracts much interests in aerospace industry due to the possibility of complex shapes and cost-effective production, most composite parts in this area are manufactured with prepregs. The reason of preference for prepregs may be the familiarity, handling, property reliability, low voids, and high fiber volume fraction.

Because it is not possible to stitch on the lay-up of prepreg sheets, there should be through-thickness holes for needle penetration in order to produce 3D structure. In this study, generation of holes are achieved by laying down prepreg tapes with a gap side by side, and by repeating this process layer by layer with different orientation. When the required thickness is obtained, the stacked prepregs have regularly-positioned holes, which will provide stitching sites for needle penetration. Terms in this paper are defined as: ‘prepreg tape’ refers to prepreg with certain width, and ‘prepreg sheet’ is the conventional prepreg. To lay down prepreg tapes with controlled gap, highly precise and automated machine is required. In this work, the automated tape placement (ATP) process has been utilized for stacking of prepreg tapes.

Fig.1: Automated tape placement process.

Fig. 1 shows ATP process, explained as follows. Prepreg tapes are pulled off the spools and delivered into a fiber placement head. They are laid down and compacted onto a mold surface by a compaction roller. At the end of the course, the remaining tows are cut and the head is positioned to the beginning of the next course. At the next course, restart rollers are activated, and tow placement (lay-down and compaction) is repeated. The heat source provides: (1) on-line consolidation of thermoplastic composites; (2) on-line debulk

and/or curing of thermoset composites. The multi-axis control of the placement head enables large-scaled composite parts with complex contoured surfaces.

In this study, a new type of 3D structure has been fabricated by combining ATP process and the through-thickness stitching. A new method is called TAPIS (Tape Placement Incorporated with Stitching). Impact performance of 2D and 3D composites has been characterized for comparison. To assess the damage after impact loading, specimens were subjected to C-scan nondestructive inspection. CAI test was also conducted in order to evaluate residual compressive strength.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sample Preparation

3D composites have been fabricated by placing the prepreg tapes in 0° and 90° with leaving small space (1mm) for the stitching yarn insertion. The slit tape was used for the placement process. It was made by slitting the roll of conventional prepreg sheet of carbon/epoxy material. Table 1 summarizes the specification of the prepreg sheet. The tape placement has been carried out by 6-axis controlled FPS (Fiber Placement System) machine as shown in Fig. 2. Fig. 3 (a) shows the roll of prepreg tapes. Without the gaps between the tapes, it can be regarded as a cross-ply laminated composite, $[0/90]_{10s}$. Any directional placement of tapes can be possible for quasi-isotropic laminates. After laying up the prepreg tapes, stitching has been conducted in the holes of 1mm x 1mm space through the whole thickness. Kevlar 29[®] fibers were utilized for stitching yarns. Fig. 3 (b) shows the stitched composite specimen for impact tests. The size of specimen is 100x150 mm with thickness of 4.7-4.8 mm. The key factors that

affect mechanical properties of TAPIS composites are the stitching process parameters. Three parameters are considered: the stitching density, the stitching pattern, and the stitching method. The stitching density has been varied by using different width of prepreg tapes: 5mm tape and 10mm tapes. For the stitching pattern, the general lock stitching and the modified lock stitching have been examined. The stitching methods by machine and handwork have also been considered.

Table 1 : Specification of prepreg sheets

Specification	USN125BX
Fiber	MISUBISHI TR50
Resin	Bisphenol A type + DICY base
Thickness	0.125 mm

Fig. 2: FPS machine for ATP process.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3: (a) Carbon/epoxy prepreg tape; (b) stitched impact specimen.

Microstructure

Fig. 4(a) and (b) show the stitch threads on the cross-sections of machine-stitched and hand-stitched 3D specimen, respectively. White area is the 0° layers, and dark one corresponds to 90° layers. In Fig. 4(a), a loop is made by two threads supplied from a needle and a bobbin, and some fibers are confined in the middle, which was pulled down upon the needle stroke. In the case of hand-stitching, only one thread is involved, and it is relatively straight as shown in Fig. 4(b). Fig. 4(c) is the longitudinal section other than the stitched area. The straightness of 0° layers demonstrates that overall placement of prepreg tapes by ATP process is excellent.

Impact Test

To examine the damage resistance of the 3D composites the low velocity drop weight impact test has been adopted. For the comparison of impact performance, 2D $[0/90]_{10s}$ laminates were also tested. The energy levels imposed to the specimens were controlled by adjusting the height of the impactor which weighs 7.96 kg with a hemisphere's diameter of 15.88 mm. Four levels of impact energy were 20J, 25J, 30J, and 35J [7]. The specimen size was 150 x 100 mm according to SACMA SRM 2R-94 test specification. The impact specimens were placed in the test fixture as specified in SACMA, and were constrained by rubber tip clamps at every

corner. For the assessment of damage after impact loading, specimens were subjected to C-scan non-destructive inspection. CAI test was also conducted to evaluate residual compressive strength of the impacted specimen.

Fig. 4: Microstructures of 3D composites: (a) a section along the 0 fiber direction incorporated with z-fibers by machine-stitching; (b) a section along the same direction with z-fibers by hand-stitching; and (c) a section along the same direction without z-fibers .

RESULTS

Compression Strength

As a reference data to evaluate the residual strength, compression test has been conducted on the un-impacted specimen. Table 2 summarizes the compression strength and modulus. Here, ORT-SH is 2D specimen laminated with prepreg sheets. ORT-05 and ORT-10 are 3D specimens using 5mm and 10mm wide prepreg tapes, respectively. The reason for lower strength of 3D specimen is due to the smaller fiber volume fraction caused by spacing for stitching. Same reason can be applied to the lower strength of 5mm taped composites. Compressive modulus of ORT-05 showed the highest value because of the reinforcing effect of stitching fibers on the specimen surface.

Table 2: Compressive test results.

Type	ORT-SH	ORT-05	ORT-10
Maximum Load [N]	20900	15880	19780
Compressive Strength [MPa]	743	670	728
Compressive Modulus [GPa]	55.7	60.0	55.6

C-Scan

Figs. 5 and 6 are C-scan images for impact energy of 25J and 30J, respectively. The damage areas indicate the pile-up images of the damage in the thickness direction. Cross stripes shown in Fig. 5 (d) and Fig. 6 (d) are the resin area formed at the gaps between prepreg tapes. Due to the acoustic impedance difference of resins from the neighboring composites, higher reflexivity of ultrasonic waves at resin areas resulted in checkered pattern. For the case of 5mm taped composites, however, cross stripes are hardly seen because the beam width of ultrasonic wave is wide enough to differentiate them in the scanned image. Images of 2D specimens show circular shapes, while those of 3D specimens are oval shape. This is because damage propagation occurs preferentially at prepreg tapes which are placed on the specimen

surfaces in the longitudinal direction. Although damage propagation is confined in both transverse and longitudinal directions due to the stitching threads, propagation is more susceptible in the longitudinal direction. The results of C-scan image clearly demonstrate that damage area of 3D specimen is smaller than that of 2D counterpart.

Fig. 5: C-scan images of 25J impact energy.

Fig. 6: C-scan images of 30J impact energy.

Impact Characteristics

Impact response

Figure 7 (a) and (b) show the load and energy histories for 2D and 3D composites. 2D composites showed drastic load drop of 4000N level and the maximum load is 9000N, approximately. 3D composites, however, resulted in a small amount of load drop in the range of 2000N, and the maximum load was less than 8000N. The large amount of load drop in 2D composites is due to that most of impact energy was absorbed in the form of delamination. In 3D composites, impact energy was absorbed in creating delamination and crack propagation in the stitching threads. The results of load-displacement showed that the magnitude of permanent deformation for 2D and 3D composites was nearly the same.

Fig. 7: Load and energy histories: (a) 2D composite; (b) 3D composites.

2D and 3D composites

Table 3 summarizes the results of the impact test, C-scan, and CAI strength of 2D and 3D composites. Damage area of 3D composites was smaller than that of 2D composites, and CAI strength of 3D composites was higher than that of 2D composites, except for ORT-05H. Among 3D specimens, ORT-05 was the best material for impact performance. Comparing the results of ORT-SH and ORT-05, 3D specimen received more energy (10%) per unit thickness, but damage area was reduced by 30%-40% than that of 2D composites. This is due to that delamination was suppressed by stitching threads. However, CAI strength of 3D specimen didn't increase greatly, because fiber volume fraction was reduced due to the gaps for stitching threads. At the energy level of 35J, most composite samples showed drastic increase of damage area and decrease in residual compressive strength. It indicates that effects of delamination suppression by stitching thread are greatly reduced above certain level of impact energy. It is also noted that all composites have nearly the same CAI strength of approximate 170 MPa after impact of 35J.

Table 3: Impact test results of 2D and 3D composites.

Properties	ORT-SH (2D)	ORT-05 (3D)	ORT-05H (3D)	ORT-10H (3D)
Impact energy/ thickness, [J/mm]	4.18 5.23 6.26 7.32	4.57 5.93 7.42 8.40	4.98 6.30 7.56 8.67	4.39 5.57 6.77 7.73
Impact energy loss/ thickness, [J/mm]	2.33 2.95 3.39 4.27	2.22 2.98 3.66 4.29	2.51 3.13 4.00 5.10	2.07 3.00 3.47 4.71
Damage area [mm ²]	994 1366 1333 1623 ±110 ±379 ±97 ±175	656 918 798 985 ±83 ±28 ±79 ±113	735 887 988 1537 ±138 ±284 ±46 ±120	798 996 1118 1293 ±97 ±213 ±254 ±116
Residual comp. strength, [MPa]	201 193 187 174 ±7 ±26 ±12 ±10	231 202 203 171 ±15 ±23 ±12 ±15	197 178 181 170 ±24 ±2 ±11 ±19	232 198 190 172 ±22 ±13 ±20 ±11

(Note) ORT-SH: 2D specimen of prepreg sheets; ORT-05: machine-stitched 3D specimens of 5mm wide prepreg tapes; ORT-05H: hand-stitched 3D specimens of 5mm wide prepreg tapes; ORT-10H: hand-stitched 3D specimens of 10mm wide prepreg tapes.

Stitching method

Comparing machine-stitched (ORT-05) and hand-stitched (ORT-05H) specimens in Table 3, the latter one resulted in larger damage area. The reason for this may be that impact energy per unit thickness is larger and the amount of stitching thread is half of ORT-05. CAI strength of ORT-05H was smaller although the damage size was larger than that of ORT-05.

Stitch spacing

Stitch spacing can be varied by using prepreg tapes of different width. Contrasting to stitching on fabrics, where fiber volume fraction barely changes upon the variance of stitching density, the fiber volume fraction of 3D TAPIS composite changes accordingly. Although ORT-10H specimen has higher fiber volume fraction, and absorbed less impact energy per unit thickness, damage area was larger than that of ORT-05H as shown in Table 3. This is because delamination suppression was less effective due to the reduced stitching density. Referring to residual compressive strength, ORT-10H had larger damage area, but the strength was higher than ORT-05H. This is associated with higher fiber volume fraction of ORT-10H.

Stitch effect

Fig. 8 shows the comparison of CAI strength of 2D and 3D composites of various stitching parameters. Although fiber volume fractions of 3D composites are lower than 2D counterpart due to the gaps for the stitching yarn insertion, the residual strength of 3D composites was higher. Improvement of CAI strength for 3D composites is due to the fact that delamination is arrested and the damage size is limited during the impact, while the delamination growth is prevented by stitching yarns during the CAI test. In the case of relatively high energy level of 35J, residual compressive strength of all type of composites didn't show much difference. It can be stated that stitching effect is negligible above the impact energy level of 35J.

Fig. 8: CAI test results.

Fig. 9: Comparison of damage area per absorbed energy.

Fig. 9 shows the average of damage area divided by impact energy per unit thickness. Since this graph demonstrates the damage area per unit energy, regardless of the magnitude of impact energy, impact performance of composite materials can be compared directly. The length scale is the standard deviation. From this figure, 3D specimens have smaller damage area than 2D counterpart. Among 3D specimens, the machine-stitched specimen using 5mm tape (ORT-05) showed the smallest damage area, and the hand-stitched specimen using 10mm tape resulted the largest damage area.

CONCLUSION

Through the comparative study on the impact performance of stitched 3D composites and 2D composites based on carbon/epoxy prepreps, the following conclusions have been achieved.

- (1) For 20J, 25J, 30J, and 35J of impact energy, the damage area of 3D specimen was smaller than that of 2D specimen. 3D composites showed less compressive strength and modulus prior to impact because the fiber volume fraction decreased due to the gaps between prepreg tapes for stitching threads. Nevertheless, CAI strength was higher in the case of 3D specimen except for ORT-05H, and the ratio of residual strength to undamaged strength increased by 7% by introducing stitching threads.
- (2) Among 3D composites, machine-stitched specimens of 5mm tape (ORT-05) showed the smallest damage area and the highest residual compressive strength. Damage area was decreased by 30-40%, and CAI strength increased by 5-10% compared with those of 2D counterparts.

- (3) Comparing between machine-stitched (ORT-05) and hand-stitched specimen (ORT-05H), the latter case showed larger damage area and smaller residual compressive strength. For the stitching density comparison, specimens of 10mm tape (ORT-10H) resulted in larger damage area than those of 5mm tape (ORT-05H) in spite of higher fiber volume fraction and smaller impact energy per unit thickness. This is because delamination suppression was not sufficient due to the less density of stitching for the case of ORT-10H.
- (4) Although CAI strength of 3D composites is enhanced by introducing stitching threads, the effect tends to decrease starting from the impact energy of 30J, and in the case of 35J all composite specimen showed similar CAI strength. Therefore, the stitching effect is negligible above the impact energy level of 35J.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by a grant from the Center for Advanced Materials Processing (CAMP) of the 21st Century Frontier R&D Program and National Research Laboratory funded by the Ministry of Science and Technology, Republic of Korea.

REFERENCES

1. Abrate, S., *Impact on composite structures*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998.
2. Schoeppner, G.A. and Abrate, S., "Delamination threshold loads for low velocity impact on composite laminates," *Composites Part A*, Vol. 31, 2000, pp. 903-915.
3. Mouritz, A.P., Leong K.H., and Herszberg, I., "A review of the effect of stitching on the in-plane mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced polymer composites," *Composites Part A*, Vol. 28 1997, pp. 979-991.
4. Byun, J-H. and Chou, T-W., "Mechanics of Textile Composites," *Comprehensive Composite Material*, A. Kelly and C. Zweben (Eds), Elsevier Science Publishers, Amsterdam, Netherlands, Vol. 1, Chapter 22, 2000, pp. 719-761.
5. Byun, J-H., Um, M-K., Hwang B-S., and Song S-W., "Impact Performance of 3D Interlock Textile Composites," Proceedings of the 4th Asian-Australasian Conference on Composite Materials (ACCM-4), Univ. of Sydney, Australia, July 6-9, 2004, pp. 488-493.
6. Shim, S-B., Ahn, K., Seferis, J.C., Berg, A.J., and Hudson, W., "Cracks and Microcracks in Stitched Structural Composites Manufactured with Resin Film Infusion Process," *Journal of Advanced Materials*, July, 1995, pp. 48-62.
7. SACMA Recommended Test Method for CAI Properties of Oriented Fiber-Resin Composites: SRM 2R-94.